

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MULTI-COMPONENT ANTI-TUBERCULOSIS DRUGS IN THE TREATMENT OF PULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS

F.K. Tashpulatova¹, S.A. Agzamova²

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute^{1,2}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14969892>

Abstract. *In order to study the effectiveness of multicomponent fixed-dose anti-tuberculosis drugs in the treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis, we examined 22 patients with infiltrative pulmonary tuberculosis, while the control group consisted of 25 patients with infiltrative pulmonary tuberculosis. A multicomponent anti-tuberculosis drug consisting of isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide, and ethambutol was prescribed to patients in phase 1. Patients in the control group received rifampicin + isoniazid + ethambutol + pyrazinamide separately for 2-3 months. At the outpatient stage, the main group received a multicomponent drug containing R450H300 for a period of 4 months, whereas the control group took these drugs separately.*

Dynamic observations showed that in the main group, the indicators of the decrease in clinical symptoms of intoxication and respiratory manifestations, decrease in MBT release, and positive radiological dynamics did not differ from the control group of patients who received the drugs separately.

Keywords: *tuberculosis, drugs, multicomponent drugs, treatment effectiveness.*

Relevance

At the current stage, the etiotropic treatment of tuberculosis involves the use of multiple anti-tuberculosis drugs. It is recommended that several medications be taken together or sequentially throughout the day to enhance the bacteriostatic and bactericidal effects at the site of infection, while simultaneously preventing the development of drug resistance in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. However, this sequential approach (involving 3 to 5-7 drugs) complicates controlled chemotherapy. Following WHO recommendations for standardized chemotherapy, which may include up to 5 anti-tuberculosis drugs per day, combined multi-component medications with fixed doses have been developed. These include combinations such as isoniazid (H) + rifampicin (R) to more complex combinations like isoniazid (H) + rifampicin (R) + pyrazinamide (Z) + ethambutol (E), packaged in vacuum-sealed blister forms containing several capsules for single administration.

Objective

The aim is to study the effectiveness of multi-component anti-tuberculosis medications in the treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis.

Materials and Methods

The effectiveness of a multi-component blister medication containing R450H300Z1500E800 was studied during the inpatient phase, alongside a two-component anti-tuberculosis medication containing rifampicin 450 mg + isoniazid 300 mg (R450H300) during the outpatient phase. The study involved 22 patients aged 27 to 63 years with newly diagnosed infiltrative pulmonary tuberculosis with cavitation. *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MBT) was

repeatedly detected by microscopy in 20 (90%) of the patients. The control group consisted of 25 patients newly diagnosed with infiltrative pulmonary tuberculosis, all of whom had MBT isolated. All patients in the study had MBT that were sensitive to first-line drugs.

The four-component anti-tuberculosis medication, containing isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide, and ethambutol, was prescribed to patients with destructive tuberculosis during the first phase (intensive, lasting 2-3 months). The control group received rifampicin 450 mg in the morning on an empty stomach, isoniazid 300 mg twice daily, ethambutol 1200 mg once after lunch, and pyrazinamide 500 mg three times a day, separately over 2-3 months.

During the outpatient phase, the main group received a two-component medication containing R450H300 for 4 months. The control group received isoniazid 600 mg and rifampicin 450 mg orally for 4 months, separately. Both groups underwent pathogenetic therapy according to an accepted scheme during the first months of treatment, including vitamin B1, B6, antioxidants (30% sodium thiosulfate 10.0 IV № 40), and a 7-day hormonal therapy with prednisolone tablets at 20 mg in a decreasing scheme, alongside detoxifying, anti-allergic, and hepatoprotective herbal preparations.

Treatment outcomes were evaluated based on the duration of symptom relief from intoxication (weakness, sweating, normalization of temperature and sleep, improved appetite, and weight gain), catarrhal symptoms (cough, reduction or cessation of sputum and chest pain), and cessation of MBT excretion, as well as radiological dynamics. In the main group receiving the multi-component anti-tuberculosis medication, a reduction in intoxication symptoms was observed within the first 10-18 days of therapy. In the control group, a decrease in intoxication symptoms was also noted within 10-20 days after the start of standard therapy. (table 1)

Table 1

Dynamics of Reduction in Intoxication in Examined Patients, Absolute Numbers (%)

Group	30 dose	60 dose	90 dose and more
Main R450H300Z1500E800	15 (68,2±9,9)	5 (22,7±8,9)	2 (9,1±6,1)
Control H600R450E1200Z1500 separately	18 (72,0±8,9) P>0,5	3 (12±6,4) P>0,5	4 (16±7,3) P>0,5

Note: R - significant difference between the main and control groups.

Before the start of treatment, the presence of Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MBT) was established in 20 (90.9±6.1%) patients in the main group. One month after the start of therapy, MBT excretion ceased in 16 (80.0±8.9%) patients (Table 2). Overall, the cessation of MBT excretion was observed in 95±4.8% of patients in the main group.

In the control group, cessation of MBT excretion after 1 month was noted in 14 (60.8±12.5%) out of 23 patients with MBT. By the end of treatment, MBT excretion had ceased in 91.3±5.6% of patients in the control group (P>0.5).

The analysis of the closure times of cavitory lesions showed (Table 3) that among patients receiving multicomponent anti-tuberculosis medication, closure of the cavity was observed in 45.4±10.6% after 3-4 months. After an additional 2 months of treatment with R450H300, another 13.6±7.3% of cavities closed.

Significant resorption of infiltration and areas of colonization was observed in 86.3±7.3% of patients in the main group after 3-4 months of treatment.

Table 2

Timing of Cessation of Mycobacterium Tuberculosis (MBT) Excretion in Patients Receiving Multicomponent Anti-Tuberculosis Medication, Absolute Numbers (%)

Patient Group	Patients with Mycobacterium Tuberculosis (MBT)	Cessation of Mycobacterium Tuberculosis (MBT) Excretion After		
		1 month	2 months	3 months
Main group, n=22	20 (90,9±6,1)	16 (80,0±8,9)	3 (15,0±7,9)	-
Control group, n=25	23 (92±5,4) P >0,5	14 (60,8±12,5) P >0,2	6 (26±9,1%) P >0,2	1 (4,3±3,2)

Note: P - significance between the indicators of the 1st and 2nd groups.

In the control group, closure of cavitory lesions was noted in 56±9.9% of patients, with significant resorption of infiltration and reduction in cavity size by the end of 3-4 months in 84±7.3% (P>0.2).

Thus, the treatment results in the control group did not differ from those of patients receiving the multicomponent anti-tuberculosis medication.

Table 3

Closure Times and Reduction of Cavity Sizes, Absolute Numbers (%)

Patient group	Closure of Cavities After		Reduction of Sizes and Resorption After		
	3-4 months	5-6 months	3-4 months	5-6 months	Overall Closure of Cavities
Main group, n=22	10 (45,4±10,6)	3 (13,6±7,3)	19 (86,3±7,3)	2 (9,1±6,1)	13 (59±10,4)
Control group n=25	14 (56±9,9) P>0,5	1 (4±3,9)	21 (84±7,3) P>0,2	6 (24±8,5) P>0,2	15 (60±9,7)

Note: P1 – significance of the difference between patients in the main group and the control group.

There were no side effects noted in patients taking the multi-component anti-tuberculosis drug. In the control group, adverse reactions in the form of toxic effects on hearing, the liver, and the nervous system were observed in 5 (20±8.0%) patients.

It is particularly noteworthy that patients with concomitant diseases of the nervous system and gastrointestinal tract tolerated the multi-component anti-tuberculosis drug well.

Thus, the multi-component anti-tuberculosis drug containing R450H300Z1500E800 is well tolerated by patients, is very convenient for administration, and, according to treatment outcomes, is not inferior to a combination of 4-5 traditional anti-tuberculosis drugs in standard dosages. It also combines well with pathogenesis therapy drugs.

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